

Higher Education's Roles as a Change Agent in the Implementation of Community Development Technology in the Independent Prosperous Village of Indonesia

Helly Ocktilia

Politeknik Kesejahteraan Sosial, Bandung, Indonesia

Email: helly_ocktilia@poltekesos.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of higher education as a change agent in developing rural communities through the application of various community development technologies. The study was conducted in a rural area in the Cianjur Regency, which was the implementation area of the Independent Prosperous Village Program of the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. This research uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The informants consisted of academics, village government bureaucrats, community leaders, and management of local institutions. The results showed that the role of change agent in carrying out community development was as a catalyst, facilitator, linker, and problem solver. These roles are carried out at every stage of community development from social initiation to evaluation. The role of a change agent has had an influence on the locality of rural communities characterized by 1) the emergence of citizen initiatives in the process of social and economic change; 2) the establishment of communication channels that strengthen the working network among residents; 3) growing mutual trust between citizens in the process of change, and 4) growing motivation to work together in developing social and economic welfare.

Keywords: *Agent of Change, Community Development Technology, Higher Education.*

INTRODUCTION

Community development is related to the process of change faced by the community. Every change requires a person or individual who guides the process of change to achieve the objectives as expected. Thus, the process of change is always marked by the presence of a person, group of people or institutions that spearheaded, mobilized, and disseminated the process of change that occurred. People who make changes are usually referred to as change agents. The name given is by the mission, which is to make a meaningful change for the community. Change agents are individuals, groups, or institutions that have the task of influencing change targets so that they make decisions in the direction they want so that change agents play a role in helping the implementation of social change or innovation that plans on society (Rogers 1983; Nasution, 1990).

Some experts suggest that change agents are interpreted as parties who want a change. It is someone or a group of people who won the trust as leaders of one or more social institutions and act as a catalyst to manage the occurring changes. Thus the change agents are professionals whose job is to assist the community or group in planning development or reshaping targets, focusing on problems, finding solutions to problems, organizing assistance, planning actions, and evaluating the results of planned efforts (Soekanto, 2009; Robbins & Coulter in Supriyanto, 2016; Rahma, et al., 2019).

Tracing the various results of research on change agents shows that change agents occupy a strategic position in society and become a medium of community aspirations where the role of change agents encourages communities so that they can solve problems independently. Knowledge, expertise, organizational experience, education, economic background are aspects that must be met by every change agent (Wahidin, et al., 2011; Rosyadi, 2012; Makowsky & Michael D., 2013). Other results show how the existence of change agents has a significant influence on the beneficiaries of the empowerment program as indicated by an increase in knowledge, awareness, changes in attitudes and behavior of the beneficiaries of the empowerment program (Sukmawati, 2013; Asep Suryana, et al., 2016).

Correspondingly, the development of rural communities carried out in several developing countries such as India, Bangladesh, and Malaysia, also shows the success of community development and empowerment programs is inseparable from the role of change agents in moving the community (Yunus, 2004; Cargill, 2008; Flax, 2017). This is in line with the opinion of Ife (1995) who argues that people in developing countries cannot function independently without the guidance and assistance of skilled change agents, who support and teach them how to work together and use their capacities

effectively. Likewise, Indonesia as a developing country that continues to improve the social welfare of its people through various empowerment and community development programs.

The main tasks of a change agent according to Rogers and Shoemaker (1985) are: (a) fostering people's desire to make changes, (b) fostering a relationship in the context of change (change relationship), (c) diagnosing problems faced by the community, (d) create a desire for change among clients, (e) translate the desire for change into tangible actions, (f) maintain the stability of change and prevent dropout, and (g) achieve a terminal relationship. Referring to these tasks, the change agents occupy a strategic position in society and become a medium of community aspirations, where the role of change agents can encourage the community to solve problems independently.

Havelock (1973) in Nasution (1988: 69-70) argues that there are 4 (four) main roles of a change agent in community development, namely: (1) Catalysts, who move the community to want to make changes, (2) as a problem solver when the community is faced with confusion in dealing with a particular problem, (3) As an assistant to the change process or facilitator, a person who can help the community in making changes from the planning stage to the evaluation; assist in the process of solving problems and spreading innovations, as well as giving instructions on how to: recognize and formulate needs, diagnose problems and determine goals, obtain relevant resources, choose or create problem-solving, and adjust and plan the stages of problem-solving, (4) as a link (linker) with the resources needed to solve the problem at hand.

Linton (1936) in Cahyono (2008), states that an anthropologist has developed role theory. According to Linton, role expectations are shared understandings that lead individuals to behave in everyday life. Someone who has a certain role is expected to behave according to that role. While Kahn et al. (in Ahmad and Taylor, 2009) introduce role theory in the organizational behavior literature. According to Kahn, an organizational environment can influence the expectations of each individual regarding their role behavior. These expectations include norms or pressure to act in certain ways. Individuals will receive the message, interpret it, and respond in various ways. Thus the role is a concept of what behavior can be carried out by individuals in society as an organization. The role can also be said as individual behavior, which is important for the social structure of society. Concerning the role of change agents, according to this theory, a person who has a role as a change agent is expected to behave according to his status. Because of this status, the change agent carries out community development per its roles as a catalyst, problem solver, facilitator, and linker.

Change agents can come from outside the community as stated by Gibson et al. in Winardi (2003) which explains that the change agent is a particular person or party, which brings an outsider's perspective to the situation of the relevant organizational change. However, change agents can also come from within the community itself, as stated by Gibson, et al., (1987) who argue that in carrying out community development change agents can come from outside community organizations (external change agents) or local communities employed at other parts of the organization (internal change agents). In practice, however, many combinations of teams of external and internal change agents are also commonly used who collaborate in implementing community development programs. Cooperation between external and internal change agents is built within a strong frame of relations. According to Ocktilia et al. (2018) a relationship is a product of communication that is created between two communicating parties so that the relationship between an external change agent and an internal change agent is built based on strong communication between the two.

One of the accelerations of community development programs in Indonesia initiated to address a variety of social welfare problems in certain areas, especially in the context of accelerating poverty reduction through the role of the environment is the Independent Prosperous Village (DSM) program. Independent Prosperous Village can be seen from the aspect of prosperity and independence. Welfare means it can solve social problems, able to meet basic needs, able to create business/employment, and able to reduce poverty, while self-reliance means to be able to optimize, access and synergize community assets, by involving 4 pillars namely the Government, Society, Business and Higher Education (Widhiowati, 2017; Directorate General of Social Ministry of Social Affairs RI, 2017). In order to accelerate social welfare, the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs is collaborating with 14 higher educational institutions in conducting social assistance in the Independent Prosperous Village (DSM) program, one of which is the Politeknik Kesejahteraan Sosial (Poltekesos) Bandung. Since 2016, the Poltekesos Bandung has conducted social assistance in the DSM program in the Sukaratu Village area of Cianjur Regency.

Poltekesos Bandung is a higher educational institution in Indonesia that prints professional social workers. In carrying out its vision and mission the Poltekesos is implementing one of the Higher Education Tri Dharma activities, namely community service activities by collaborating student practicum activities through Community-based Macro Social Work Practices activities with the social assistance activities of the DSM Program. In this practicum activity, there are academics namely lecturers and students who act as change agents who carry out social assistance by implementing various technological innovations in community development. To get a picture of how the role of universities as change agents in community development in Sukaratu Village, a study was carried out by examining aspects of the role of change agents as catalysts, facilitators, problem solvers, and linkers in implementing various community development technologies.

METHOD

The research method used is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach (Creswell, John W., 2016). This qualitative research was conducted to examine how the role of universities as change agents in community empowerment. In the process of community empowerment, it is seen how the role played by the change agents together with the citizens who are the target of empowerment. Descriptive methods are used to examine, explain, and describe the roles played by change agents through the DSM program. Data and information from primary data sources were obtained purposively based on the consideration of the informants being able to provide accurate information about the role of STKS Bandung as a change agent implementing community empowerment in Sukaratu Village as a village implementing the DSM program.

Data and information obtained through in-depth interviews and observations to informants consisting of Academics (lecturers and students), Government Bureaucrats (Village Heads), Community Leaders, and Local Institution Managers (Chair and Secretary of the Social Welfare Center and Joint Business Group Managers). The total number of informants is 7 (seven) people. Qualitative data analysis is carried out continuously from the beginning of the research process to the end of the research. Starting from the data collection stage, then data reduction, presentation, and drawing conclusions and verification (Sugiyono, 2015). Data processing and analysis are carried out with exploratory studies using an inductive approach, with steps: reducing data, presenting data, summarizing data, and verifying data.

RESULTS

General Description of Research Location

Sukaratu Village is located in Gekbrong Subdistrict, Cianjur Regency, Indonesia, with an area of 941,410 ha / m² with a population of 6,132 people and 1,835 households. The designation of Sukaratu Village as the location of the implementation and development of the Independent Prosperous Village Program in West Java Province has been running for 3 (three) years since 2016-2019. The social changes achieved by this village have been quite a lot, marked by the increased capacity of Human Resources (HR) in managing and developing local organizations and socio-economic activities in the region. The existence of Poltekesos Bandung as a change agent in performing community development in Sukaratu Village is carried out by involving an external change agent (Poltekesos Bandung) with an internal change agent, namely community cadres, community leaders, administrators of local institutions, and village government bureaucrats.

The roles of change agents are performed based on the stages of macro social work practices ranging from social initiation, social organizing, and assessment, preparation of intervention plans, social interventions, and evaluation. While the techniques and technology used in each stage of the community development process are Community Involvement technology, Home Visit, Transect Walk, Focus Group Discussion, Methodology of Participatory Assessment (MPA), Social Mapping and Technology of Participation (ToP). (Tropman, John, E., 1995; Elison, 1997; Netting, 2012; Bambang Rustanto, 2002, Practical Guidelines III, 2017).

The Role of Change Agencies as Catalysts and Facilitators

The initial role of the change agent in carrying out community development in Sukaratu Village was carried out to move the community to make changes. The implementation of this role as a catalyst greatly influences the emergence of local community initiatives, where the involvement of citizens in the processes of social and economic change raises awareness of the needs, problems, potential and resources and assets that can be utilized to overcome these needs and problems. The role of a catalyst in community development in Sukaratu Village was applied to the stages of social initiation and social organizing.

The social initiation phase is the stage undertaken to build community trust in external change agents. Trust building is important to do because the building of trust and the closeness of the change agent with the community will affect community support and participation in the implementation of the DSM Program. Some of the community development techniques and technologies used by the change agents at this stage are:

1. Home visit, i.e., the change agent conducts home visits to several elements of the community, such as hamlet heads, RW heads, RT heads, community leaders, community cadres, and administrators of various organizations and community groups.
2. Transect walk, i.e. the change agents and community representatives who understand the environment of Sukaratu Village to trace the area of Sukaratu Village to recognize the condition and situation of the region, village boundaries, community assets, as well as sources and potential that can be used as a source system in community development.
3. Community involvement, namely the change agent immersing themselves in the activities of the Sukaratu Village community such as community service activities, Integrated Service Posts (Posyandu), recitation, sports, and other community activities.

The results obtained through social initiation are good acceptance from the community, building community trust, and establishing social relations between the Change Agencies and the people of Sukaratu Village. Social organizing is the next step undertaken by change agents. At this stage, the change agent acts as a catalyst and facilitator with the aim of building agreements with the community in raising issues of perceived problems and needs and discussing alternative solutions to problems using the potential and resources available in the village. Some of the community development techniques and technologies used by the change agent are community meetings and focus group discussions. This technique is applied by change agents through meetings with various elements of society and raising community issues felt by the community and discussing them in a focused manner, so that information is obtained about the needs and problems felt by the community. During the social organizing phase, activities were also carried out to identify various local organizations and local leaders who were judged to be providing support for the community development programs to be designed.

The result of social organizing is the establishment of an agreement between the change agent and the interest group, which is a group of people who are willing to be actively involved in activities to be designed for development. Furthermore, the interest group or Internal Change Agent is referred to as the Community Work Team.

The Role of Change Agents as Problem Solvers and Linkers

The role of a problem solver and linker is carried out when the change agent is faced with a situation where the community has difficulty when facing and dealing with problems. The change agent will move to assist the change process. This role is applied in 4 (four) stages of community development, namely social assessment, intervention planning, intervention, and evaluation.

Social assessment is the next stage after the change agent has carried out social initiation and social organizing. Social assessment is carried out to obtain comprehensive data and information on issues that occur in Sukaratu Village. Assessment is one of the processes in the practice of social work that is the process of understanding and disclosing problems, needs, potentials and sources or assets of the community through data collection activities, data analysis, and concluding, so that information is obtained about the potential and sources available or needed to deal with the problem. The community development technology used is the Methodology of Participatory Assessment (MPA), which is a participatory method used to identify needs, make a mapping of community conditions, and analyze the ability of the community to plan the sustainability of a running program. Implementation of MPA by the change agent is done by involving all major stakeholders. The change agent acts as a facilitator for the community members in the implementation of the MPA which is held through a community meeting to determine the phenomenon of problems that exist in Sukaratu Village.

The application of the MPA was carried out by giving out colorful meta cards and stationery to the community, then participants wrote down 1 (one) type of problem in the Sukaratu region. The meta card is then affixed to the flipchart that has been provided. Based on various problems that arise, a discussion is held to determine the priority of the problem which will be followed up together with the community. The results of the social assessment agreed that the problem of poverty with a focus on handling the problem of school dropouts and Women with Socio-Economic Vulnerability (PRSE) was determined as a priority problem.

In the next step, the change agent facilitates participants to recognize the area and identify the potential and sources and assets of the community in each of the areas in Sukaratu Village. At this stage the Participatory Social Mapping technique is used, in which the community is asked to draw a map of the area of the hamlet where they live, then identify the various potentials and sources as well as community assets in the village area by attaching symbols in the form of people or buildings in each part of the area where the source or the community's assets are. There are five types of assets in the community, namely physical assets, human assets, social assets, financial assets, and environmental assets (Green and Haines in Fedryansyah (2017), Dahlan (2017)). Based on the results of Participatory Mapping obtained information about the potential, sources and assets of the community as presented in the following table:

Table 1. Potential, Resources and Assets of Sukaratu Village Community

No	Type of Community Assets	Shape of Assets
1	Physical Assets	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Worship facilities: 16 mosques, 25 prayer rooms, 44 majelis taklim 2. Educational Facilities: 4 (four) Early Childhood Education (PAUD), 4 (four) Elementary Schools, 2 (two) open Junior High Schools, 1 (one) Ibtidaiyah Madrasah (MI) 3. Health Facilities: 1 (one) Village Health Post (Poskesdes), 4 (four) Integrated Service Posts (Posyandu)
2	Financial Assets	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Village Consultative Body (BPD) tasked with accommodating the aspirations of the community through deliberation media and setting these aspirations together with the village head

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Empowerment of Family Welfare (PKK) is a social organization that empowers women to participate in development 3. The Social Welfare Center (Puskesmas) functions to carry out social service activities in a synergistic and integrated manner between community groups. 4. Social Welfare Institution (LKS) Societa Indonesia: LKS that handles the problem of abuse of Narcotics, Psychotropics, and Addictive Substances (NAPZA) and Children Facing the Law (ABH), 5. The Community-Based Social Welfare Facility (WKSMB) consisting of Early Childhood Education (PAUD) schools, madrasah diniyah, Integrated Service Posts (posyandu) for children under five and pregnant women, and Integrated Development Posts (posbindu) for Seniors
3	Social Assets	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Ngaos</i>: the tradition of reading the holy book of the Qur'an that colors the daily lives of the community 2. <i>Mamaos</i>: a cultural art that illustrates the subtlety of character and taste which becomes the glue of brotherhood and kinship in the community's social relations 3. <i>Maenpo</i>: is a typical martial art known as pencak silat martial art, art that is displayed at celebratory activities or when there are guest visits
4	Human Assets	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More than 65% of the population are productive age and 35% are non-productive with a predominance of age between 0-15 years 2. Woman Social Welfare Leader (WPKS) consisting of PKK cadres, posyandu cadres and posbindu cadres 3. Two professional social workers 4. There are 30 trained Community Social Workers (PSM) 5. One person from the District Social Welfare Workers (TKSK)
5.	Natural Assets	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Area of 941,410 ha/m2 2. Resources in the agriculture and tea plantations sector 3. Tourism potential: Sanghiyang Tread Site (historic stone, Flat Stone (flat-shaped stone), Pesantren Dam, and Pacaku Stone

Source: Research results by Helly, Yuti S.I., Binahayati R., (2020)

Intervention Planning is the next stage carried out by the change agent. At this stage, the change agent acts as a facilitator and linker to make participatory intervention plans using the Technology of Participation (ToP), a participatory community development planning technique, so that all parties have the same opportunity to express ideas and appreciate the ideas of others. The steps in implementing the ToP are as follows:

1. Stage I : Discussion

The discussion stage is a guided dialogue with a series of questions related to the issue of women with socio-economic vulnerability and out of school youth guided by the facilitator. The questions posed are at four levels of awareness, namely: Objective, Reflective, Interpretative, and Decisional (ORID). The ORID structure allows participants to explore from the superficial to deep understanding

2. Stage II : The Workshop

The workshop stage is a way to facilitate the thoughts of the participants in the group about the subjects that are designed in dealing with the problem of women with socio-economic vulnerability and out of school youth so that they become a focused decision and action..

3. Stage III : Formulation of the Action Plan

This stage is a combination of the discussion phase and the workshop stage. The aim is to draw up a real plan of action in the form of activities for handling problems including identifying the source system needed.

The implementation of *Technology of Participation* (ToP) produces a work plan as presented in the following table:

Table 2. Sukaratu Village Community Development Work Plan

No	Problem	Needs	Work plan	Source System
1	Limited knowledge and understanding of women with socio-economic vulnerability to local economic business development strategies	Increasing the capacity of women with socio-economic vulnerability to developing local economic ventures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Socialization of Joint Business Groups (KUBE) 2. Socialization of the Family Empowerment (PEKKA) program 3. Training on making food products for banana weevil chips 4. Training in packaging, marketing, and developing a network of food products 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assistant of KUBE in Cianjur Regency 2. PEKKA Manager in Cianjur Regency 3. PKK cadres 4. Cianjur Regency Industry Office 5. Business World in the neighborhood of the Sukaratu Village
2	Limited knowledge and accessibility of dropouts to social services	Increased knowledge and accessibility of out of school children to social services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education about education awareness 2. Pursuing Equality Exam Program A, B, C Packages. 3. Distance Education Program (PJJ) 4. Training on resource mobilization in strengthening productive economic endeavors 5. Giving reinforcement and motivation for students 6. Sharing and Fun Education 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Social Service of Cianjur Regency 2. Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) Subdistrict of Gekbrong 3. Shelter and Social Rehabilitation in Cianjur Regency 4. Harapan Mekar Gekbrong Community Learning Activity Center (PKBM) 5. PGRI High School 1 Cianjur Tourism 6. Community Teaching Village 7. The Bright Reading Room Movement (GERBANG) of Cianjur Regency 8. SMP Open Sukaratu (Parent Middle School 1 9. LKS-IPWL Societa Indonesia

Source: Research results by Helly, Yuti S.I., Binahayati R., (2020)

Based on the work plan that has been prepared, subsequently, the change agent performs the role as a linker that is the community liaison to the source system needed to realize the work plan. In carrying out the role of a linker, the task of the change agent is not only to provide guidance on accessible sources but also to introduce the target group to the intended sources, follow up, and distribute resources, and to ensure the target group receives social services. At this stage the change agent and TKM contact the parties who will be asked to become resource persons and instructors and agree on the material and time of the activity.

The next stage carried out by the change agent is the social intervention, which is the stage where the intervention plans that have been formulated are implemented into activities. At this stage, the change agent takes on the role of facilitator and problem solver by providing technical assistance, managerial assistance, and organizing the necessary training following the needs of the target group. Furthermore, the realization of the work plan through intervention is facilitated by the change agent in the following two forms of activity:

Table 3. Social Interventions in Community Development at Sukaratu Village

No	Implementation of Activities	Initial Conditions	Final Conditions
1	<p>Increasing the capacity of Women with Socio-Economic Vulnerability:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Socialization of the Joint Business Group (KUBE) by the KUBE companion of Cianjur Regency 2. Dissemination of the Family Head Empowerment (PEKKA) program by the PEKKA manager in Cianjur Regency 3. Training on making banana weevil chips food products by Sukaratu Village Chips Entrepreneurs 4. Training on packaging, marketing and development of a network of food products by Cianjur Regency Industry Office 	<p>Limited knowledge and understanding of women with socio-economic vulnerability to local economic business development strategies</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing the understanding and comprehension of women with socio-economic vulnerability to local economic development strategies 2. Information obtained about the PEKKA program which can be used as a source system for developing local economic ventures 3. The development of the marketing area of food products 4. The development of the PRSE network with partner institutions, namely PT. Sumber Alfaria Trijaya (Alfamart) Cianjur and PT. Tirta Investama (Aqua) Cianjur
2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Counseling about education awareness by MUI Coordinator of Gekbrong District 2. Socialization of skills training at the Social Care Institution of Youth (PSBR) by Social Workers from Cianjur Regency Social Rehabilitation and Rehabilitation 3. Pursuing equality Exam Program Packages A, B, C. By the Executive Board of the Community Learning Activity Center (PKBM) Harapan Mekar Sukaratu 4. Distance Education Program (PJJ) by PJJ SMA PGRI 1 Tourism Coordinator in Cianjur 5. Training on resource mobilization in strengthening productive economic endeavors by the Cianjur Regency Social Service and the Village Teaching Community Chair 6. Sharing and Fun Educating by the Shining Reading Room Movement (GERBANG) of Cianjur Regency and Societa Indonesia LKS-IPWL 	<p>Limited knowledge and accessibility of school dropout children in social service programs</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing public awareness and understanding of the importance of education for children. 2. Obtained information about the pursuit equality test system package A, B, and C. 3. Obtained information about the existence of skills training for school dropouts for free. Youth Social Institution (PSBR4). 4. Information is obtained about the PJJ program that makes it easier for the community to access education. 5. Increased knowledge of out-of-school adolescents about ways to mobilize resources to strengthen productive economic enterprises 6. Increasing public awareness of the problem of school dropouts in Sukaratu Village

Source: Research results by Helly, Yuti S.I., Binahayati R., (2020)

Evaluation is the last step carried out by the change agent. Evaluation is a process of assessing the effectiveness of interventions that have been implemented in terms of both process and achievement of results. Evaluation activities were carried out with participants consisting of Community Work Teams, Village Government Bureaucrats, representatives of KUBE management, and school dropouts. This activity includes an evaluation of each series that has been carried out both from the beginning to the end of the intervention. The evaluation stages are carried out by: (1) Facilitating the group to measure or score the level of success in achieving the goals of change; (2) Facilitating the group in measuring or giving a score on the success rate of the process that has been undertaken. In general, the evaluation results show the successful implementation of social interventions. This can be seen from the participation of citizens in planning and participating in quite large activities, where their presence and activity in meetings conducted in formulating problems, planning interventions, and implementing interventions.

DISCUSSION

Substantial community development is the process of community restructuring by proposing self-participatory models in managing and organizing socio-economic life to enable people to meet their own needs compared to the previous period (Ife in Zubaedi, 2016). This is in line with the opinion of Ife & Tesoriero (2008) in Helly O., (2019) which explains that the pattern of community development will lead to an outcome because the expected process will put the community in a position to determine their own goals in managing a community development pattern. In proposing participatory self-help

patterns models a figure who has sufficient competence to build relationships with the target group, so that trust is built to fuse in the models offered. The figure is known as the change agent, which is a person or group of people who have an important role in bringing change to society. The results showed that academics from the Poltekesos Bandung became change agents who had the task of developing the community of Sukaratu Village to become an independent prosperous village by offering and implementing a self-help model so that the community could be more independent in meeting their needs.

Academics, in general, assume the role and task of being change agents amid the target group. Their efforts as change agents are to accompany and direct the wishes of citizens in the process of taking innovation or new ideas. In carrying out their duties, there are 4 (four) roles carried out by the change agent, namely as a catalyst, facilitator, linker, and problem solver (Havelock, 1973). In line with the opinion of Havelock, Roger (1995) suggests that change agents perform 7 (seven) roles in carrying out community development as follows:

1. Fostering a need among citizens towards a change. In the early stages, change agents help the people of Sukaratu Village to become aware of the need to change old attitudes and behaviors. In this case the change agent acts as a catalyst to build public awareness to change.
2. Establish an information exchange relationship. To support change, agents need to develop harmonious relationships with citizens. In this case, the change agents mingle with the people of Sukaratu Village in the process of social initiation joining in various activities in the community and organizing social organizations. At this stage, the change agent has the role of being a facilitator by conducting community meetings and focus group discussions with elements of the community to obtain an overview of the phenomenon of problems that exist in the community as well as the potential and resources needed to handle it.
3. Diagnose the community. Change agents are responsible for identifying and formulating problems faced by citizens to clarify why existing alternatives are not able to meet their needs. At this stage, the change agent motivates the residents of Sukaratu Village together to conduct a social assessment to identify the problems, needs, potential, resources, and assets of the community needed to deal with the problem and formulate it into a work plan.
4. Cultivate a strong desire among the people for change. After the change agent discloses various alternative actions that enable citizens to realize their goals, he then tries to motivate citizens to be interested in making changes. At this stage as a facilitator, the change agent motivates and moves Sukaratu Village residents to develop an intervention plan that contains activities to be carried out to deal with problems faced by the community.
5. Translating desire into real action. Change agents try to influence people's behavior so they want to take new ideas that come from outside. At this stage, the change agent becomes a problem solver to intervene by moving the community to actively participate in taking concrete actions from the intervention plan that has been formulated.
6. Stabilize the process of taking new ideas and prevent the interruption of the innovation process. Change agents can foster new behavior among citizens by conveying messages that strengthen citizens who have adopted new ideas and subsequently standardize them into new behaviors. This step is sought when citizens are at the stage of implementation or confirmation of taking ideas or innovations, meaning that this step is a series of interventions carried out in a participatory manner by change agent together with the target group and the Community Work Team.
7. Establish a final relationship. The ultimate goal to be realized by change agents is to grow the ability among citizens to improve their conditions independently. Change agents in this context need to position themselves as actors who develop the ability of citizens to foster change independently

In general, the assisting process carried out by the change agent in carrying out community development in Sukaratu Village has been going well, but if it is related to Roger (1995), there is a role that has not been implemented by the change agent, which is the role in creating a final relationship in fostering community independence. This role largely determines the sustainability of conditions that have been achieved by the people of Sukaratu Village. In the welfare aspect, there has been a significant change that has been achieved, namely the development of productive economic endeavors by the Women with Socio-Economic Vulnerability Group (PRSE) and the development of accessibility of out of school children towards social services in education. But in the aspect of independence, the community still needs further assistance until they are considered truly independent. An illustration of the flow of change agents' roles in carrying out community development is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The Flow of the Role of Change Agents in Carrying Out Community Development

CONCLUSION

The results showed that the role of higher education as change agents was carried out through the application of various community development technologies such as Methodology of Participatory Assessment (MPA), Participatory Social Mapping, Technology of Participation (ToP), etc. The stages of the process of community development are carried out through 6 (six) stages, namely: social initiation, social organizing, assessment, preparation of intervention plans, social interventions, and evaluations. At each stage, the roles played by the change agent are the catalyst, facilitator, linker, and problem solver.

The role of change agents has influenced the locality of rural communities characterized by: 1) the emergence of citizen initiatives in the process of social and economic change; 2) the establishment of communication channels that strengthen the network among citizens; 3) growing mutual trust between citizens in the process of change; and 4) growing motivation to work together in developing social and economic welfare. The presence of change agents who work together with the community is very beneficial for their lives. Change agents become the main key that acts as the motor of community drive in rural community development.

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